

E-Learning Development Strategy of the University: Comparative Study

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Abstract

The development of e-learning as an object of management in higher education institutions, as a rule, corresponds to a simple model of transition from the stage of initiative implementation at the level of individual teachers, departments or divisions to the stage of centralized strategic management of the implementation of e-learning tools, processes and methods at the institutional level. Although the development and application of e-learning technologies in the educational process is still an individual innovation, today it is part of the national policy for the development of higher education and affects the assessment of the effectiveness and competitiveness of universities. It means that institutional e-learning development strategy bridges the individual innovation activity of teachers and national priorities in quality and accessibility of higher education. Therefore, the objective of the research is to summarize, compare and study the e-learning development strategies of the higher educational institutions from EU, Russia, Australia and South-Asia to distinguish major types of the strategies, as well as tools and mechanisms embedded to achieve strategic goals. As a result of the comparative analysis of 20 e-learning development strategies of universities authors offer recommendations for the strategy structure depending on the functional and evolutionary type of the strategy that were identified in the paper. This research was funded by RFBR, project number 20-010-00571 "The Impact of Digital Transformation on Improving the Quality and Innovation of Services".

Keywords: e-learning, development strategy, university management.

1 Introduction

E-learning can best be described as the science of learning without the use of instructional material printed on paper but with the use of networked information and communication technology. E-learning is emerging as the paradigm of modern education with the progress of the development of information and communication technology. The great benefits of e-learning include liberating interactions between learners and teachers, through the asynchronous and synchronous learning network model, from time and space constraints (Sun, Tsai, Finger, Chen & Yeh, 2008). To describe this mode of teaching and learning, a number of other terms are also used including online learning, virtual learning, distributed learning, networking, and web-based learning. Although the term E-learning involves much more than online learning, since the letter "e" in E-learning stands for the word "electronic" and it would include all educational activities carried out by people or groups working online or offline with the use of information and telecommunication technology (Naidu, 2006).

E-learning has emerged as a promising solution to lifelong learning and on-the-job workforce training over the past few years. For companies to ensure that employees and channel partners are equipped with the latest information and advanced skills, and effective training methods are crucial (Akberdina, Kalinina & Vlasov, 2018; Aleksandrov et al., 2018). Rushing to fulfil this need, universities around the world are now offering thousands of online courses, including degree and certificate programs.

In 2001, MIT announced its commitment to making available, for non-commercial use, materials from virtually all of its courses freely on the Web (Shea, 2002). An advantage of e-learning over Instructor-led training (ILT) is that it can be developed and delivered much more quickly and can be used by a large population spread all over the world at the same time. It gives new role to the university as the driver for economic growth and social well-being (Karpov, 2017).

The worldwide market of e-learning services hit \$222 billion funding in 2020, according to EdTechXGlobal data. The average annual growth rate is estimated at 7-10% in the next three years and it means the market will rise to \$282 billion of dollars (Edumarket.digital, 2021). It shows that e-learning can be a strong and cost-effective alternative to studying in the classroom. As an integral part of academic and technical education, e-learning will keep rising. Efforts can continue to explore how a more enticing and reliable online learning experience can be developed. One approach to do this is to incorporate effective pedagogical approaches, to increase interactivity and personalization of the method, and to involve learners more (Zhang, Zhao, Lina-Zhou & Nunamaker, 2004).

2 Strategic management of E-Learning

2.1 Development of E-learning as a system

E-learning have grown over the last decade to encompass multiple modes of education and transmission of learning through collaborative and individual efforts (Tabor, 2007). In order to provide widespread collaborative participation and open access through the Internet and online networking, new technologies have been developed. In addition to new technologies, pedagogical approaches have been built to include various kinds of course models, giving learners both compensation and the ability to start learning synchronously and asynchronously (Dron & Anderson, 2014). A variety of competitive developments continue to be faced by the higher education industry, from higher levels of student competition to questions around higher tuition fees and, as a result, student debt.

While this is definitely a positive development to extend higher education to meet a larger and more diverse community of people, it is also a significant barrier for universities, which have to achieve better results with less funding. This is a regular occurrence, intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic, in developing countries such as Brazil. According to the Ministry of Education, 38 of Brazil's 69 state institutions have shut down completely in October 2020, with 21 teaching remotely and 12 remaining partially open. According to the government, approximately half of the more than 1.1 million students enrolled in federal institutions have had their studies halted. Conforming to surveys conducted by The Lemann Foundation and Datafolha in November 2020, the transition to online tuition has been impeded by the lack of computer and internet access among the country's poorest pupils. States were left to make their own options because there was no national plan to support the transition. Students' biggest concerns remain a lack of desire and difficulty sticking to a schedule, according to the survey results, which show that over 40% of students share devices to do their homework from home.

The emphasis on more strategic uses of e-learning is becoming relevant as the environment in which higher education institutions work evolves affecting their primary and secondary markets as well as their instructional and organizational structures. It is generally recognised that technology, demographics, government policy and economic strength are the main external factors of change (Fisser, 2001; Middlehurst, 2003; Wende & Ven, 2003). E-learning could be described as an open system of individuals (students and teachers) and non-human objects (systems of learning management and information systems) that are managed to maximize the results of e-learning and student satisfaction (Figure 1). As a purposeful system, the E-learning paradigm is synergistic. There is a dynamic interaction between the inspiration of students, the quality of course design, teaching roles, and the academic efforts of students.

Figure 1. System view of e-learning, (Ashill & Nicholas, 2018).

The variety of existing models shows that the introduction of e-learning in higher education should be considered as a development project that can have a positive impact on building the capacity of the university and improving the effectiveness of its activities. The development and implementation of such a project is based on the tools of strategic management and change management, project management and organizational development. Strategic management is the ongoing planning, monitoring, analysis and assessment of all the criteria that an entity requires to accomplish its priorities and goals in long term period. E-learning development can be included as a part of educational, marketing or commercial strategy as well as strategy of internationalization or strategy of digital transformation. It could cover the whole university or be specific for the certain department or even discipline. In this study, the authors summarize and compare the e-learning development strategies of the higher educational institutions from Europe Union (EU), Russia, Australia and South-Asia. With this collected information, the findings show that e-learning development strategy process matches the traditional pattern shown in the Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Strategic management plan.

The figure 2 helps to explain where is the focus of this article, section 4 strategical analysis, when we try to analyse current e-learning development strategies of different universities. To start, we need brief evidence of the national policies for the development of e-learning in higher education as its affects the institutional policies and competitiveness of universities.

2.2 National policy in e-learning development

New technologies foster innovation, however, it is people who are the real source of creativity. The government's position in the strategy was to provide the infrastructure to allow imagination, innovation and cooperation to drive the country forward as an international pioneer in our emerging digital environment by generating high-value content for itself and exporting it to improve growth and global competitiveness in the areas of e-learning, e-health and online gaming. The Bologna Implementation Report shows that "For new technologies to be used in an effective, efficient and trustful way in teaching and learning in higher education, certain framework conditions need to be met (Vatolkina, Fedotkina, 2018)... Action required for the implementation of these changes needs long-term strategic planning, changes in the legal environment and financial resource allocation". According the report, 38 EHEA member states have implemented some kind of national strategies or policies on the use of new technologies in teaching and learning. For example, small-scale initiatives have been developed by the National Agencies in Norway (NOKUT) and Sweden (NAHE) on quality standards for e-learning, and recommendations have been drawn up in the UK (QAA) on the quality evaluation of distance learning. Nevertheless, e-learning quality is not included as a regular or integral part of national quality reviews in any country, nor is any emphasis placed on the standards and guidelines established by the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) on the quality in e-learning. Other organisations, such as the National Association for Developmental Education (NADE, Norway), the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC, UK), and the Higher Education Academy (HEA, UK) have focused on the methodological development of e-learning assessment (The Horizon report, 2008). In "Bologna Digital 2020. White Paper on Digitalisation in the European Higher Education Area" universities should accordingly change their strategies and administration process to adopt e-learning and go in line with relevant national policies European Commission, 2018; Rampelt, Orr & Knoth, 2019). It will require transformation in all components of education management system at the university (Lyapuntsova, 2020).

The Australasian Council on Free, Distance and E-Learning (ACODE), which has published detailed benchmarks to impact policy and practice at institutional, national and international levels, is another experience. The Council on Higher Education Accreditation (CHEA) has established standards in the United States for the accreditation and quality assurance of distance learning, and the Distance Education and Training Council (DETC) has defined, maintained and promoted education excellence in distance education. In Russian Federation specific goals for the development of e-learning is set in the Federal project "Young Professionals" for the years 2018-2024 including number of MOOC created by the universities and number of tertiary students who has experience in formal e-learning.

3 Methodology and Results

3.1 Methodology of the study

This article was developed aiming for summarizing and compare the e-learning development strategies of the higher educational institutions from European Union (including the United Kingdom), Russia, Australia and South-Asia to distinguish major types of the strategies, as well as tools and mechanisms embedded to achieve strategic goals. This work is based in qualitative analyses from 20 universities, therefore, six universities from the Great Britain (GB), one university from the Netherlands (NL), one university from Switzerland (CH), four universities from Australia (AU), two universities from New Zealand (NZ), four universities from Russian Federation (RU), one university from China (CN), one university from Singapore (SG).

The analysis is based on the strategies adopted by these universities focusing on the implementation and use of digital technologies for teaching and learning in the last decade. Content analysis was implemented as

research method. Content analysis is a quantitative analysis of texts and text arrays with the aim of subsequent meaningful interpretation of the identified numerical patterns. The following stages of content analysis are distinguished: determination of units of analysis; calculation of frequency distributions; interpretation of the results obtained.

Categories and units of content analysis are highlighted in the context of the study objective: a) type of e-learning strategy; b) vision of university e-learning strategy; c) strategic strands and relevant goals of the e-learning development strategies. Such an analysis allows to obtain reliable results when comparing organizations belonging to the same type of economic activity.

Content analysis show that there are following two major types of e-learning strategies:

1. Specific Digital Education Strategy presented as independent document covering objectives and tools in the field of e-learning or broader digital education strategy or distance education strategy;
2. E-learning strategy as the part of the other strategy - overall Institutional Strategy or Digital Strategy or Digital Campus Strategy or Overall Education Strategy.

There are key drivers for universities to embrace digital learning and to achieve our objectives we will deliver the vision of the universities that understand which role e-learning plays in university development to engage locally or globally.

Table 2. The strategic visions in digital learning of the higher educational institutions from EU, Russia, Australia and South-Asia.

University		University's Vision on digital education strategy	Type of strategy
1	University of Oxford (GB)	The goal is to ensure that Oxford remains a premier institution for teaching, adopting the very best of teaching innovations that are made possible by digital technology.	<u>Specific Digital Education Strategy</u>
2	University College of London (GB)	To establish a digital learning infrastructure that connects students with each other, with staff, with research and with the wider world.	<u>Digital Learning is the part of the Institutional Education Strategy</u>
3	University of Surrey (GB)	The digital learning strategy provides a vision of how an institution can nurture and sustain a rich portfolio of digital learning opportunities.	<u>Specific Digital Learning Strategy</u>
4	University of Greenwich (GB)	The University aims to provide a secure, reliable and feature rich digital environment for learning, teaching, research and professional services now and in the future, as technologies and the educational environment evolve.	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of overall Strategy</u>
5	University of Leicester (GB)	Developing digital skills and capabilities are strategic priorities for the University of Leicester as it works towards the ambition of becoming a "discovery-led university" that is "ever more focused on innovation	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital</u>

			<u>Campus Strategy</u>
6	Ulster University (GB)	Empowering people through digital;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital Strategy</u>
7	Tilburg University (NL)	<u>Digital Education Enhancement Program (DEEP) is designed to achieve: 1 Enhanced learning: the digital enhancement of personal learning and development. 2 Enhanced collaboration: the creation of a modern, networked learning community. 3 Enhanced support: digital educational logistics and support that nurture TiU-shaped professionals.</u>	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of the Institutional Strategy</u>
8	University of Geneva (CH)	The Digital Strategy is a tangible expression of the University's global vision, presenting a series of objectives aiming to strengthen the institution's digital activities and projects, as well as helping to develop new initiatives, thereby contributing to the digital transformation that is underway in society and in the world of academia;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital Strategy</u>
9	University of Wollongong (AU)	Our digitalisation priority will see us pursue projects and redesign processes to enhance our digital capacity and teaching, learning and research practices.	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of the Institutional Strategy</u>
10	University of South Australia (AU)	The University of South Australia will be recognised internationally for its use of innovative digital technologies to deliver a compelling and industry-relevant learning experience for students;	<u>Specific Digital Learning Strategy</u>
11	The University of Melbourne (AU)	Melbourne graduates will be sought after for their creativity, their rigorous and ethical approach, their social awareness about global challenges and their readiness for an increasingly digital and changing world;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of the Institutional Strategy</u>
12	Griffith University (AU)	Griffith's strategy is to be at the leading edge of digital innovation to enhance the student experience and Griffith's reputation as a university of influence;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital Strategy</u>
13	University of Auckland (NZ)	To become a customer-focused organisation, the University requires a customer experience design capability. This capability consists of a design-thinking practice guided by meaningful analytics and by continuously-updated customer-journey models, and facilitates co-design processes in which customers participate directly;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital Strategy</u>
14	University of Otago (NZ)	The University will be known for its leadership and excellence in teaching, learning and support of distance students and its distance education programme will reflect the University's distinctive contribution to national and international education;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Distance Education Strategy</u>
15	Higher School of Economics (RU)	The university's strategy in the field of online learning is aimed at creating models of the educational process using online courses and providing conditions	<u>Specific Online Education Strategy</u>

		(organizational, financial, technological, methodological, personnel) to increase the effectiveness of such models;	
16	The Southwest State University (SWSU) (RU)	Information and communication technologies are widely used in education. ICT technical means have formed new directions in education, such as e-learning, mobile learning, online learning, and distance learning. One of these areas - distance learning, appeared on the basis of distance learning and nowadays has become popular in general education;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Distance Education Strategy</u>
17	St. Petersburg State Electrotechnical University (RU)	The strategy in the field of e-learning and distance learning technologies (is a formalized set of principles coordinated with the development priorities of the university, on the basis of which an action plan is formed to saturate the educational process with information and communication technologies;	<u>Specific E-learning and Distance Education Strategy</u>
18	The Chinese University of Hong Kong (CN)	Enhance critical thinking and self-learning skills, using eLearning and innovative pedagogies, to nurture students as lifelong learners and global leaders;	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Institutional Strategy</u>
19	Singapore Management University (SG)	In the face of massive digital transformations, we can spearhead cutting edge ideas for business and public sector transformation, leveraging digital solutions, contributing to a better understanding of the impact of digital transformation on customer and citizen experience, and offering solutions for the management of such impact;	<u>Vague e-learning strategy as part of Digital Transformation within Institutional Strategy</u>
20	Ural State Law University (RU)	<u>Ural State University of Law requires active implementation of e-learning tools and distance learning technologies at all levels of training, wide representation on online educational platforms, and participation in promising projects.</u>	<u>Development of e-learning is the part of Specific Digital Strategy</u>

Table 1 identifies the analysed universities, shows the vision of each university on digital education strategy and also describes in which level its strategy is in its portfolio. The analysed strategies are available in full through their electronic addresses mentioned in the bibliographic reference of this article.

The proposed strategies stand on a pre-analysis of the where the university stands on the adoption of digital education technologies, due to its engagement being very much driven by the particular needs of individual departments and faculties or the enthusiasm of individuals. It took the view that institution-wide engagement is needed to bring about a more coordinated approach to new developments and a better understanding of the benefits of technology use.

It was understood that the institution own values are great guiding influence to implement the strategy successfully. As suggested by UCL's strategy "The Introductory Programme" is a tool to explore and to integrate interdisciplinary academic activities into the university, building an online student's community. The summary of the strategies analysed consist of three main strands to achieve the digital implementation triumphantly. Firstly, it stands on to achieve excellence in education through implementation of e-learning and digital technologies, fostering innovation and constantly looking for the new possibilities in implementation of digital technologies to improve quality and accessibility of higher education. Secondly, strategies seek to offer support for teaching and administrative staff. This aims to augment the use of innovative tools and spaces for collaborative learning, relevant training and resources. Online learning is the product of student participation, rooted in a rich immersive online learning environment, in a range of online activities. Online learning experiences of high quality give students a multitude of ways to collaborate and interact with content, learning materials, instructors and peers. They are diverse and fast-paced, and therefore, to a large degree, freeing

students from time and location constraints. Thirdly, to provide proper digital infrastructure to connect students with staff, with other students, with research and with the outside world, promoting support network interdisciplinary education. All universities strategies studied in this article, agree on providing a high-quality technology blended environment for staff and students. This strategy step carries a physical infrastructure development needed to facilitate the use of systems and boost accessibility inside or outside its campus.

Based on the twenty universities' strategies above we analysed specific goals according to three strategic strands identified in the strategies. These goals are evaluated in the table 2.

Table 3. The three strategic strands and relevant goals of the e-learning development strategies.

Strategic strand		The goals
1	Achieve excellence in education through the implementation of e-learning and digital technologies	To extend the areas of excellence in digital education that already exist and to ensure that all departments and faculties regularly review how digital methods might enhance their teaching and learning provision.
		To continue to support local innovations by providing incentives and mechanisms for their development, and increase activity to maximise their impact.
		To use appropriate digital technologies to develop more inclusive provision for different learning needs
		To improve the student digital experience, providing a high quality, technology-rich blended environment for student study.
		To develop the digital skills and capabilities of students and staff
		To enhance digital leadership skills
		To engage in digital activities across disciplines and in national and international digital communities of practice
2	Support students and staff in the implementation of e-learning and digital technologies	To support academic staff as innovative teachers by developing the functionality and usability of key digital platforms, world-class tools, support To support students by making collections of resources more accessible and relevant to their learning.
		To provide routinely available training on good practice in e-learning
		To change the role that we play within the University to become a trusted partner that empowers and supports our students and staff.
3	Development of digital infrastructure and relevant resources	To support the development of remote teaching by provision of a robust platform, standard templates
		To support the development of an enabling infrastructure for the use of students' own devices in teaching events, and future-proof it.
		To support the development of an enabling infrastructure for online assessment
		To clarify, and agree the resources needed to develop digital education
		To provide a distinctive digital infrastructure to connect students with each other, with staff, with research and with the outside world
		To forge strategic partnerships and leverage resources outside the University to accelerate our ability to deliver solutions

Table 2 demonstrates the finding of this research which are three strategic strands of the e-learning development strategies and suitable goals. The guiding principles behind the proposed strategies, such as

supporting students and employees and introducing supporting infrastructure, were designed to ensure reliable and effective delivery for a university's core customers: academics, students, and professional services workers, with a focus on defining the possible digital state commodity and the future trends.

The implementation of strategies will require a number of economic, organizational, social and technological innovations at the universities including: curriculum design innovations, introduction of digital scholarships for staff, changes in staff motivation mechanisms, development in student-centered learning, introduction of digital micro-credentials, decentralized planning, improvements in feedback mechanisms (Akberdina, Kalinina, & Vlasov, 2018). Implementation of e-learning development strategies require innovations in strategic partnership management as an important resource of the content and technologies (Smirnova, Lazarou, Vatolkina & Dascalu, 2019).

The deployment strategy is the inspiration and attention of academic workers and it should be directed by students. In order to encourage and support departments and faculties, units work with the Enhanced Learning Technology team and establish their own priorities for the application of the use of new educational technologies. The Strategy sets out certain criteria for good practice for departments and faculties to be followed, such as defining local priorities with inclusivity in mind and recommending strategies to ensure continuity of online learning. It also encourages departments to consider the complexity of their practices, noting the number of digital technologies that can be applied across the university or elsewhere.

If the strategy is well implemented the following objectives can be delivered.

- Providing further chances for face-to-face encounters between teaching staff and students and between students and experts in the industry
- Supporting students to get involved with the industry
- Enhance the use of emerging technology to create genuine resources for experiential learning
- Provide versatile and tailored learning experiences to enable students through their degree to have more control of their success.
- Professionals with the requisite digital skills to succeed in their future careers
- Enable employees in improving digital literacy and the opportunity to assess and incorporate emerging digital technology into their teaching practices

4 Conclusion

Digital and Information Services are the future of education, therefore creating strategies to implement them successfully is the key to step ahead to the digital age and potentially improve learning, teaching and researching at any University. So much of what the University is seeking to achieve will be enabled digitally. This paper concludes with three strategic strands of high-impact to enhance e-learning effectively in universities, through the analysis of strategies of the higher educational institutions from EU, Russia, Australia and South-Asia. First, achieve excellence in education through the implementation of e-learning and digital technologies. The implementation of a framework for digital capabilities would enable universities to assess the needs of the customer, to set up training programs and to design experiences. Second, support students and staff in the implementation of e-learning and digital technologies. Providing sufficient professional instruction, through learning, supporting structures for students and academic workers, making the limits of space, time and distance no longer complex problems and the universe of questions open to dynamic discovery. Third, the development of digital infrastructure and relevant resources. To ensure and deliver an integrated, robust, agile and sustainable digital learning environment, investment in the framework of information systems is needed.

Furthermore, since e-learning is becoming worldwide, while innumerous universities are still struggling on the adaptation to this new era, this study provides strategies three strategic strands as ways to ensure that they can actively and effectively engage in e-learning.

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